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DIVIDEND POLICY AND SHAREHOLDERS' WEALTH: EVIDENCE FROM SOME QUOTED BANKS IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the impact of dividend policy on shareholders' wealth using a panel data of some quoted Banks in Nigeria for a period ranging from 2010 - 2014.

The Fixed Effect Model was employed on the panel data in order to study the impact of dividend policy on shareholders' wealth in Nigeria. Data were collected from the Annual Reports of the Banks used for the various years under study.

From the empirical result, a positive and robust significant relationship was found to exist between Dividend Per Share (DPS) and Shareholders' wealth with a t -statistics value of (2.940719). A positive significant relationship was also found to exist between Retained Earnings (RE) and Shareholders' wealth with a t -statistics of (7.621971). However, Earnings Per Share (EPS) was found to exert a robust negative significant relationship with shareholders' wealth with a t -statistics value of (-3.528975).

This study concluded that the dividend policy of a firm has an impact on its shareholders' wealth as supported by the Dividend Relevance theory which explains that dividend policy has significant effect on shareholders' wealth as well as firms' value.

This study therefore, recommends that firms should operate a dividend policy that tends to satisfy the need of shareholders as well as the investment need of the firm. Thus, a portion of the earnings of a firm should be paid as dividend while a portion is also retained for further investments.

Keywords: Dividend Per Share, Shareholders' Wealth, Earning Per Share, Fixed Effect Model.

1 Introduction

Dividend policy chosen by a firm has a way of maximizing shareholders wealth. The primary objective of any organization is to maximize the wealth of shareholders. Financial manager's aim is to take a decision in such a way that shareholders receive the high contribution of dividend which leads to increase the price of share. Miller and Modigliani views dividend as irrelevant, under a perfect market situation for firms in the same risk class as firm dividend can only be influenced by earnings and the market price of a firm. Since the firm is faced with the decision of apportioning fund to retention for firm growth and paying out profit as dividend, it is the firm's earnings as opposed to dividend that determines the value of a firm (Ozuomba, Okaro & Okoye, 2013). The effect of dividend policy on shareholders wealth is important to management, investors who plans their portfolios. Some scholars believe that dividend policies are irrelevant in determining the wealth of shareholders while others argue that dividend policies are relevant and greatly influence the wealth of shareholders (Ozuomba, Okaro & Okoye, 2013). Miller and Modigliani, and Litner and Gordon have contributed greatly to the ongoing debate on dividend policy's effect on shareholders' wealth. The optimal dividend policy is the one that maximizes the company's stock price which leads to maximization of shareholders' wealth. This study is interested in the following question: Does dividend affect shareholders' wealth? However, this has been an unresolved issue. It is on this premise that this study intends to empirically analyze the impact of dividend policy on shareholders' wealth.

The remaining part of this study is sectioned as follows: Section two reviewed relevant literature on the subject matter, Section three discussed the methodology adopted in analyzing the data obtained, Section four focuses on estimation and discussion of results. Lastly, Section five concludes the study with the necessary recommendation made.

2.0 Literature Review

2.1 Concept of Shareholders' Wealth

Shareholders' wealth is the present value of the expected return that shareholders will get from the companies that they have invested. Shareholders can benefit from their investments when the stock price appreciates or an increase in dividend payments (Akit, Hamzah, & Ahmad, 2015). Shareholder's wealth is defined as the present value of the expected future returns to the owners (Shareholders) of the firm. These periodic returns can take the form of periodic dividend payments and/or proceeds from the sale of Stock. Shareholders wealth is

measured by the market value of the firm's common stock. Shareholders' wealth is represented in the market price of the company's common stock, which, in turn, is the function of the company's investment, financing and dividend decision (James & John, as cited in Azhagaiah & Priya, 2008). Managements' primary goal is shareholders' wealth maximization, which translates into maximizing the value of the company as measured by the price of the company's common stock.

Shareholders' wealth is mainly influenced by growth in sales, improvement in profit margin, capital investment decisions and capital structure decisions (Azhagaiah & Priya, 2008).

2.2 Concept of Dividend and Dividend Policy

According to Paramasivan and Subramanian (2009), Dividend refers to the business concerns net profits distributed among the shareholders. It may also be termed as the part of the profit of a business concern, which is distributed among its shareholders. According to the Institute of Chartered Accountant of India, dividend is defined as a distribution to shareholders out of profits or reserves available for this purpose. Dividends could be described as payment made out of the company's earnings to Shareholders after the obligation of all fixed income earners has been met (Arowoshegbe, 2009). SEC (2000) in its guideline defines dividends as the percentage or the amount of that proportion of net profit of a company declared payable to its investors. On his part, Orojo (as cited in Arowoshegbe, 2009) defines dividends as the sum of money which is received by a Shareholder as his share of the profit earned by the company, measured by his shareholding or part of the asset which are divisible among Shareholders. Dividends can be defined as the distribution of earnings (past or present) in real assets among the shareholders of a firm in proportion to their ownership (Kapoor, as cited in Ozuomba, Okaro & Okoye, 2013). Dividends can be in the form of cash, stock, stock split, stock repurchases, and regular dividend payment, e.t.c. (Ozuomba, Okaro & Okoye, 2013). Ozomba et al. (2013) states further that Dividends are used by management to maintain a certain level of earnings in a firm and sustain the prices of shares in the stock exchange.

Dividend policy represents agreed guidelines which regulate management decision in sharing profit to shareholders (Ashamu, Abiola, & Badmus 2009). Kurfi (2006) described dividend policy as a standard policy with respect to the payment of cash dividends. Pandey (1999) sees dividend policy as a decision by the financial manager whether the firm should distribute all profit or retain them or to distribute a portion and retain the balance. ICAN (2009) argued that the dividend policy of a firm relates to the various decisions on payment of dividend and

states that the critical question in dividend policy is whether profits should be distributed as dividends or retained within the firm to finance future expansions and growth.

The factors that determine and shape the dividend policy of firms according to Malla (2009) includes legal requirements, liquidity position of the firm, firm's internal policies that enshrines the need to repay debt through retained earnings, restrictions enshrined in debt contracts and the tax position of shareholders.

2.3 Dividend Per Share (DPS) and Shareholders' Wealth

Dividend policy is explained as how much a company's earnings should be given to shareholders and how much should be retained by the firm for investment purposes (Chenchehene & Mensah, 2015). Dividend policy refers to management's long-term decision on how to deploy cash flows from business activities—that is, how much to invest in the business, and how much to return to shareholders (Nitta, 2006).

Iqbal, Waseem, and Asad (2014) examine the impact of dividend policy on shareholders' wealth in context of Pakistan. Thirty-five (35) companies randomly from three sectors; Textile, Sugar and Chemical are observed in the study. The annual data for these companies from 2006 to 2011 is used in the study. Simple OLS technique for analysis was used to derive the results of the study. The findings showed that dividend policy of the firm has significant positive impact on shareholders wealth.

Ordu, Enekwe and Anyanwaokoro (2014) examined the effect of dividend payment on the market prices of shares of quoted firms in Nigeria. The study examined 17 quoted firms using time series on dividend per share, dividend yield and dividend payout ratio that ranges between 2000 and 2011. The model specification for the analysis of data was the ordinary least squares techniques applied as panel estimation. The researchers' empirical results arising from the panel least squares suggest a positive effect between market price per share and dividend per share confirming that a rise in dividend per share brings about an increase in the market price per share of quoted firms.

Chenchehene and Mensah (2015) examined the effect of dividend policy on shareholders wealth in the UK retail industry from 2004-2008. With this, 25 firms from the retail industry in the UK were selected. The variables adopted in the study are earnings, profitability, share price, firm size, leverage and investment. The results indicate that, firm size, current dividend

payout and current investment do not have much significant effect on shareholders wealth. However, variables such as earnings, profitability, share price, leverage, investment and dividend payout lagged one year have significant effect on shareholders wealth. In all, the result indicates that dividend policy has positive effect on shareholders wealth.

Ojeme, Mamidu, and Ojo (2015), examine empirically, the implications of adopted dividend policies on the value of shareholders' wealth and the extent to which dividend policy affects the market value of shares in quoted banks in Nigeria. The paper focuses on the situation before and after the financial meltdown. Correlation results of dividend paid in 2007-2010 and their corresponding market value showed that payment of dividend by quoted banks is relevant to their market value and the amount paid as dividend affects the value of their share. Ansar, Butt, and Shah (2015) examine the relationship between shareholders wealth and dividend policy. Sample of 30 companies from Karachi stock exchange was selected which includes companies from textile, cement and chemical sector. Shareholders wealth is measured with the market price of shares. Dividend per share, retained earnings, lagged price and return on equity was used as independent variables. The estimation based on multiple regression model shows that there is strong relationship between shareholders wealth and dividend policy. The shareholders wealth is increase by dividend policy in case of Pakistan.

Emeni and Ogbulu (2015) conducted a study on the relationship between dividend policy and market value of firms in the financial services sector of the Nigerian economy. The study used panel data constructed from the financial statements of firms listed on the NSE for a period of 10 years, from 2002-2011. These financial statements were obtained from the NSE Fact Book. The Ordinary Least Square (OLS) statistical technique was used for the data analysis. From the results of the study, cash dividend, stock dividend and investment policy have a negative but not significant relationship with the market value of firms in the financial services sector of Nigeria, while earnings was found to have a positive and insignificant relationship with market value (though significant at 10% level of significance). Generally, the result is in tandem with the dividend irrelevant hypothesis of Miller and Modigliani, that dividend policy has no effect on market value of firms.

Akit, Hamzah, and Ahmad (2015) examine the impact of dividend policy on the shareholders' wealth of Shariah and non-Shariah compliance companies listed in Bursa Malaysia main market. A sample of 274 Shariah compliance companies and 129 non-Shariah compliance companies listed on Bursa Malaysia for the period of 2004 to 2013 has been

selected. The results are obtained through two-way Fixed-Effect Generalized Least Squares (GLS) regression for Shariah compliance companies and random-effect GLS regression for non-Shariah compliance companies. The identified determinants are dividend per share (DPS), retained earnings per share (REPS), return on equity (ROE), lagged price earnings ratio (PER_{t-1}), financial leverage (DTE) and firm's size (lnTA). The results indicate that the measurements for dividend policy (DPS and REPS) are significant determinants of shareholders' wealth for both Shariah and non-Shariah compliance companies.

H₁: There is no significant positive relationship between dividend payment and shareholders' wealth.

2.4 Earnings Per Share (EPS) and Shareholders' Wealth

According to Ward (1993) owner's wealth maximization comes as a result of profit maximization. Salih (2010) found a positive significance relationship between Earnings per Share (EPS) and market value for the full UK market; however, this result was different when based on individual economic sectors. Merton (1985) opines that dividend is a mechanism for conveying missing information on earnings to the markets. Therefore, the market value of a company does not respond to dividend policy but rather to unexpected earnings. Taking a sample of 3,800 observations for the period 1988 to 1993, Conroy, Eades & Harris (2000) found that earnings announcement can provide sufficient information to the markets making dividends sound like an additional mechanism for signals. In a study in China, Chen, Firth & Gao's (2002), used 1,232 announcements of listed companies for the period 1994–1997 and found that the market value of a company is closely associated with unexpected earnings and that cash dividends play only a limited role regarding this signal. Taking a sample of 164 corporations, Gordon (1959) tested 3 hypotheses that there are 3 reasons why investors buy shares namely (1) dividend and earnings (2) dividend and (3) earnings. Using a cross section data, he found that it was difficult to conclude that the market value of an organization is impacted positively by dividend and earnings. In the second hypothesis (dividend) he also found that there is no significant and positive relationship between the market value of a corporation and dividend. Based on the result from the third hypothesis, a dividend increase will lead to an increase in the market value of a company and a reduction in the cost of equity.

Using an event study to test abnormal returns around the dividend announcements, Brown, Finn & Hancock (1977) found that a change in both dividend and earnings have a positive relationship with abnormal returns, however, only the impact of dividend is statistically significant. Using a sample consisting of 352 observations of quarterly dividend and earnings announcements from 1979 to 1981; Kane, Lee & Marcus (1984) finds that the market tends to evaluate both the dividend and earnings announcements jointly. Furthermore, there is a positive and significant relationship between dividend and market value; and also between earnings and market value. In their study in the German market, Amihud & Murgia (1997) took a sample of 200 companies over a period of five years and found that earnings has an interpretation power on share price movement. Likewise, taking a sample of 150 companies on the Nigerian Stock Exchange, Nwaka (2012) finds that the earnings of listed companies in Nigeria proxied in his study by Earnings Per Share (EPS) has a positive and significant relationship with share prices. Emeni and Ogulu (2015) conducted a study on the effect of dividend policy on the market value of firms in the financial services sector in Nigeria. The study used panel data constructed from the financial statements of firms listed on the NSE for a period of 10 years, from 2002-2011. These financial statements were obtained from the NSE Fact Book. The Ordinary Least Square (OLS) statistical technique was used for the data analysis. From the results of the study, cash dividend, stock dividend and investment policy have a negative but not significant relationship with the market value of firms in the financial services sector of Nigeria, while earnings was found to have a positive and insignificant relationship with market value (though significant at 10% level of significance).

H₂: There is no significant positive relationship between earnings per share and shareholders' wealth.

2.5 Retained Earnings and Shareholders' Wealth

Retained earnings are the percentage of net earnings, which are not paid out as dividends, but retained by the company to be reinvested or to pay debt. Findings by Oladipupo and Okafor (2011) implied that retained earnings have significantly positive with shareholders' wealth. Khan (2009) also stated that higher share prices are consequences of higher retained earnings. This was also proven by Al-Troudi and Milhem (2013) in their study where the relationship between REPS and closing price of firm's stock is positive and highly significant. Studies by Gul, Sajid, Razzaq, Iqbal and Khan, (2012) and Joshi (2012) also confirmed the relationship. However, Bhana (1992) found that there is no guarantee that the retained earnings will be

translated into an increase in shareholders' wealth. Oladipupo and Okafor (2011), in their research work titled "*Control of shareholders' wealth maximization in Nigeria*" focused on parties controlling shareholders' wealth maximization and the ways it affects the firm's performance. The data used for the study were collected from the Nigerian stock exchange and the annual reports of six sample firms from food / tobacco and subsector for 20 years. The data collected were analyzed using ordinary least square (OLS) regression, autocorrelation and auto regression. The study showed that all the predictor variables provided good explanation. The firm size (FS) and retained earnings (RE) had positive relationship with each other and their impact on the shareholders' fund was proved statistically significant, while dividend payment had negative relationship with the shareholders' wealth. However, *turnover* and *retained earnings* were of more significance in controlling the shareholders' wealth than the dividend payout.

H₃: There is no significant positive relationship between retained earnings and shareholders' wealth.

2.6 Theoretical Framework

2.6.1 Dividend Irrelevance Theory

The theory presented by Miller and Modigliani (M &M) suggested that the shareholders wealth is not increased by the dividend policy of the firm. Shareholders wealth depends upon solely on the earning capacity of the firm. By giving dividends to shareholders the company is adding more risk as they increase the amounts of debt so the gain for shareholders is offset by the added amount of risk (Miller & Modigliani, 1961).

M&M demonstrated that under certain assumptions about perfect capital markets, dividend policy would be irrelevant. Given that in a perfect market dividend policy has no effect on either the price of a firm's stock or its cost of capital, shareholders wealth is not affected by the dividend decision and therefore they would be indifferent between dividends and capital gains. The reason for their indifference is that shareholder wealth is affected by the income generated by the investment decisions a firm makes, not by how it distributes that income. Therefore, in M&M's world, dividends are irrelevant. M&M argued that regardless of how the firm distributes its income, its value is determined by its basic earning power and its

investment decisions. They stated that “...given a firm’s investment policy, the dividend payout policy it chooses to follow will affect neither the current price of its shares nor the total returns to shareholders” (p.414). In other words, investors calculate the value of companies based on the capitalised value of their future earnings, and this is not affected by whether firms pay dividends or not and how firms set their dividend policies. M&M go further and suggest that, to an investor, all dividend policies are effectively the same since investors can create “homemade” dividends by adjusting their portfolios in a way that matches their preferences.

According to Al-Malkawi, Rafferty, and Pillai (2010), M&M based their argument upon idealistic assumptions of a perfect capital market and rational investors. The assumptions of a perfect capital market necessary for the dividend irrelevancy hypothesis can be summarized as follows: (1) no differences between taxes on dividends and capital gains; (2) no transaction and flotation costs incurred when securities are traded; (3) all market participants have free and equal access to the same information (symmetrical and costless information); (4) no conflicts of interests between managers and security holders (i.e. no agency problem); and (5) all participants in the market are price takers.

2.6.2 Dividend Relevance Theory

Relevance theory explains that dividend policy has significant effect on shareholders wealth as well as firms’ values. The proponents of this theory consider dividend decision to be an active variable in influencing shareholders’ wealth. Examples of such proponents are Gordon and Lintner. The main idea of their theory is that even in perfect markets, the uncertainty of future situation is a sufficient reason to change the price of a share. Gordon (1959) argues that investors are generally risk averse and attach less risk to current as opposed to future dividends or capital gains. Therefore investors prefer to receive certain money today than to wait for gains from a questionable future investment. Hence, the dividend policy does matter. This forms the basis for the Bird in Hand theory propounded by Lintner (1956) and Gordon (1959). The Bird in hand theory also referred to as the traditional view of the theory of dividends emphasized that dividends are the singular determinant of the value of shares and that the receipt of the share of profits now, in form of income rather than in the future, in form of capital appreciation, enhances the value of the share (ICAN 2009). The payment of dividend helps to resolve the uncertainty in the mind of investors about the future earning

potentials of the company. Investors place greater reliance on the ability of the firm to earn profits in the future and pay dividends, reduce the risk perception of the company and this increases the value of the company's shares, all things being equal. Linked to the present study, this theory presupposes that dividend payout impacts on shareholders' wealth because it reduces the uncertainty in the mind of the investors making them to discount the firm's return at a lower rate, thereby resulting into higher market values.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Data and Data Source

The data were collected from the Annual reports of the Banks quoted on the floor of the Nigerian Stock Exchange as at 31st December, 2014 for the period under review (i.e. 2010-2014). The Population of the study was the entire fifteen (15) Banks quoted on the floor of the Nigerian Stock Exchange as at 31st December, 2014. And the sample size of thirteen (13) was derived using Yaro Yamane (1967) sample size formula as shown below:

$$n = N / 1 + N (e)^2$$

Where: n = sample size

N = Population of the study

e = Level of significance. Thus, with a level of significance of 10%,

$$n = 15 / 1 + 15 (0.10)^2$$

$$n = 13.$$

3.2 Model Specification

The model for this study was a modification of study of Salman, Lawal, and Anjorin (2015) conducted a research on "the impact of dividend policy on the share price of selected quoted firms in Nigeria" using the model below:

$$MPS = \alpha + \beta_1 DPS + \beta_2 EPS + \mu$$

Where α = Intercept β = Parameter estimate (coefficient) MPS = Market price per share DPS = Dividend per share EPS = Earnings per share μ = Error term.

Therefore, for the purpose of this present study, the above model was modified thus:

$$SHW = \beta_0 + \beta_1DPS + \beta_2EPS + \beta_3RTE + \varepsilon$$

Where: SHW = Shareholders' wealth (proxy by total shareholders' fund)

DPS = Dividend Per Share;

EPS = Earnings Per Share;

RTE = Retained Earnings;

ε = Error term;

β_0 = Intercept of the relationship; and

$\beta_1 - \beta_3$ = Unknown coefficients of the variables.

Apriori Expectation are stated as:

$$\beta_1 > 0, \beta_2 > 0 \text{ and } \beta_3 < 0$$

3.4 Data Estimation Technique

To estimate the model, the Fixed Effect Model was used to analyze the model.

4.0 ESTIMATION RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Estimation Results

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

	SHF	EPS	RE	DPS
Mean	114.8627	78.15698	2814333.	1.95E+08
Median	83.00000	50.00000	13819000	1.83E+08
Maximum	874.0000	874.0000	1.50E+08	5.13E+08
Minimum	-158.0000	-85.00000	-2.74E+08	-1.36E+08
Std. Dev.	149.1460	131.0110	86595784	1.33E+08
Skewness	2.617819	4.467578	-2.029078	0.228454
Kurtosis	14.34694	27.94308	7.417678	2.878290
Jarque-Bera	331.8503	1491.738	76.46709	0.475106
Probability	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.788555

Source: Eviews 8.0

An examination of the descriptive statistics of the variables as shown in table 1 above, it can be observed that Shareholders fund has a mean value of 114.8 which indicate that on the

average most companies in the sample will likely disclose their value of their share in the stock market this is also reflected in the minimum and maximum values respectively .The standard deviation measuring the spread of the distribution stood at 88.3 which indicate that the observation are well spread with respect to a normal distribution. An evaluation of the Jarque-Bera statistics for the variable reveals that it satisfies normality $P=0.00$ when tested at 5% level of significance. A further examination of the explanatory variable reveals that they are normally distributed with a $p=0.00$ when tested on 5% level.

Table 2: REGRESSION RESULT: FIXED EFFECT MODEL

Dependent Variable: SHF				
Method: Panel Least Squares				
Date: 03/30/16 Time: 09:39				
Sample (adjusted): 2012 2014				
Periods included: 3				
Cross-sections included: 10				
Total panel (unbalanced) observations: 25				
Convergence achieved after 10 iterations				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
EPS	-232183.6	65793.50	-3.528975	0.0047
DPS	299686.1	101909.1	2.940719	0.0134
RE	1.985287	0.260469	7.621971	0.0000
C	2.01E+08	20831312	9.654789	0.0000
AR(2)	0.633062	0.173910	3.640176	0.0039
Effects Specification				
Cross-section fixed (dummy variables)				
R-squared	0.995936	Mean dependent var	2.27E+08	
Adjusted R-squared	0.991133	S.D. dependent var	1.37E+08	
S.E. of regression	12931747	Akaike info criterion	35.88729	
Sum squared resid	1.84E+15	Schwarz criterion	36.56986	
Log likelihood	-434.5911	Hannan-Quinn criter.	36.07660	
F-statistic	207.3615	Durbin-Watson stat	1.790529	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			
Inverted AR Roots	.80	-.80		

Source: Eviews 8.0

The table above shows the regression result conducted using the fixed effect model to examine the effect of the independent variables Earnings per share (EPS), and Dividend per share (DPS) and retained earnings on the dependent variable (Shareholders' fund).

From the table above the coefficient of determination denoted as R^2 stood at a value of 0.99 which shows that the model explains about 99% of the systematic variation exhibited by the dependent variable Shareholders' fund while other factors not included and captured by the stochastic error term explains a proportion of 1%. However the adjusted R^2 which adjust the degrees of freedom for inclusion of successive variables into the model stood at a value of 99%. The F-stat value is used to test for the goodness of fit of the model. The decision rule is to accept the F stat as significant if the probability value is less than 0.05 otherwise rejected. From the table it was observed that the F-stat value of 20.7 and an associated probability value of 0.00 is less than the critical value 0.05 and hence we accept the model because it gives a clear indicator that there is a linear relationship existing between the dependent and independent variables. Also the result indicates that we can be confident that the model will be able to explain the actual behaviour of Shareholders' fund of companies in Nigeria. The Durbin Watson statistics as shown in the table above stood at a value of approximately 1.8 which shows that the presence of first order spatial correlation does not hold hence the regression coefficients will not be biased.

An evaluation of the slope of the coefficient of the explanatory variables reveals the existence of a negative relationship between Earnings per share (EPS) and Shareholders' fund (SHF) which was also found to be highly significant at 5% ($P= 0.00 < 0.05$) indicating that there is a significant relationship between Earnings per share and Shareholders' fund. Therefore, we accept the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant positive relationship between EPS and shareholders' wealth. Dividend Per Share (DPS) which is measured as dividend divided by the number of ordinary shares has a positive effect on Shareholders' fund (SHF) indicated by the slope coefficient which is highly statistically significant at 5% as the probability value is less than 0.05 ($p= 0.00 < 0.05$). Retained Earnings (RE) was found to have a positive relationship with shareholders' fund. It was also found to be statistically significant when tested at 5% level of significance.

Table 3: HAUSMAN TEST

Correlated Random Effects - Hausman Test			
Equation: Untitled			
Test cross-section random effects			
Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	53.764630	3	0.0000

Source: Eviews 8.0

This test was carried out to see if the random effect model will be more appropriate for estimation so as to choose between the random and fixed effect model. An examination of the estimated chi-square, we reject the hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the estimated coefficients of the two models. It seems there is no correlation between the error term and one or more regressors. Hence, we can reject the random effects model in favour of the fixed effect mode

Table 4: Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey

F-statistic	0.273736	Prob. F(3,43)	0.8440
Obs*R-squared	0.880780	Prob. Chi-Square(3)	0.8301
Scaled explained SS	1.728696	Prob. Chi-Square(3)	0.6306

Source: Eviews 8.0

In recognition of the fact that the problem of heteroscedasticity is mostly encountered in cross sectional data, the Breusch-Pangan-Godfrey test was performed on the residuals as a precaution. The result showed probabilities in excess of 0.05 which leads us to reject the presence of heteroscedasticity in the residual

Table 5: Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test:

F-statistic	0.238131	Prob. F(2,40)	0.7892
Obs*R-squared	0.553023	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.7584

Source: Eviews 8.0

The Lagrang Multiplier (LM) test for higher order autocorrelation is utilized in this study owing to the fact that it tests for high order autocorrelation and is relatively more powerful than the Durbin Watson test. From the hypothesis of zero autocorrelation, the residuals were not rejected. This was because the probability (prob. F , chi square) were greater than 0.05. The LM test did not therefore reveal the problem of first order spatial correlation in the model.

4.2 Discussion of Results

In line with a priori expectation, Dividend Per Share (DPS) was found to exert a positive statistically significant relationship on Shareholders' wealth which was proxy by Shareholders' Fund (SHF), as it reported a t-stat value of 2.940719. This finding is in tandem with the findings of Brown et al. (1977), Kane et al. (1984), Ordu et al. (2014), Ojeme et al. (2015), and Ansar et al. (2015) who all found a positive relationship between DPS and shareholders' wealth. However, this finding was at variance with the findings of Gordon (1959), Oladipupo and Okafor (2011), and Emeni and Ogbulu (2015), who found a negative relationship between DPS and Shareholders' wealth.

Earnings Per Share (EPS) was found to exhibit a robust negative relationship with shareholders' wealth as it reported a t-stat value of -3.528975. And in relation to the literature reviewed, this finding was at variance with the findings of Brown et al. (1977), Kane et al. (1984), Salih (2010), and Nwaka (2012) who found EPS to have increased shareholders' wealth.

Lastly, Retained Earnings (RE) was found to have a very robust positive relationship with shareholders' wealth as it reported a t-stat value of 7.621971. This finding corroborated with the findings of Khan (2009), Oladipupo and Okafor (2011), and Al-Troudi and Milhem (2013) who found a positive relationship between Retained Earnings and Shareholders' wealth. However, this finding was at variance with the findings of Bhana (1992) who found a negative relationship between Retained Earnings and Shareholders' wealth.

5.0 CONCLUSION AND POLICY IMPLICATION

The central objective of this study was to empirically analyze the impact of dividend policy on the wealth of shareholders owing to the fact that it has been an unresolved issue whether

the dividend policy of a firm has impact on its shareholders wealth, as revealed by extant literature.

Dividend policy has been seen as a decision by the financial manager whether the firm should distribute all profit or retain them or to distribute a portion and retain the balance. From the research findings above, Dividend Per Share (DPS) and Retained Earnings (RE) were found to have a positive significant relationship with Shareholders wealth. Thus, confirming the Dividend Relevance theory which explains that dividend policy has significant effect on shareholders wealth as well as firms' values. The proponents of this theory consider dividend decision to be an active variable in influencing shareholders' wealth. Examples of such proponents are Lintner (1956) and Gordon (1959). However, Earnings Per Share (EPS) was found to have a robust negative relationship with shareholders wealth.

From the empirical results above, Dividend Per Share (DPS) and Retained Earnings (RE) both of which are important components of a firm's dividend policy were found to have a positive relationship with shareholders' wealth. This study therefore recommends that firms should operate a dividend policy that tends to satisfy the need of shareholders as well as the investment need of the firm. Thus, a portion of the earnings of a firm should be paid as dividend while a portion is also retained for further investments.

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